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Supplement of

Reclaiming the memory of pioneer female geologists 1800–1929

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Female geologists, 1800-1929

Female geologists (Earth Sciences, excluding astronomy & prehis), 19th century & 1900-1929

legend anthropo: anthropologist; B:botanist; con.:connection;c rystallo: crystallographer; D.: Dsc; g:geologist; fed.: federation; geogr: geographer; gl: glacial; h.: honorary; his: history
ill: illustrator; mineral: mineralogist; mu: museum; n.g.: not geologist; or.:origins; pb: palaeobotanist; pedo.: pedologist; pt: palaeontologist; petro: petrologist; petrol:petroleum;
Ru: Russian; strati:stratigrapher; t.y.: too young to be included in the list; UK: British; uni.:university; USA: American; w: webpage

last name	last name (married)	first name	birth	marr.	death	PhD/Dsc	nationality	discipline- subject	mentored by a woman	pair sorority ?
Adametz	Kittl	Lotte	1879		1966	–	Austrian	g	–	–
Adams	Fenton	Mildred	1899	1921	1995	–	USA	pt, g	–	–
Adamson	Hobson	Margaret	1837			–	Australian	ill, fossil collector	–	–
Alexander	–	Annie M.	1867	–	1950	–	USA	pt (vertebrate), zoologist	–	n.g.:M iss Wemple ,Louise Kellogg
Anderson	Gray	Elizabeth	1831	1856	1924	–	UK (Scottish)	pt, fossils collector	–	J. Donald Longstaff
Andrews	–	Mary K.	~1853	–	1914	–	Irish	gl geomorphologist	–	S. Thompson
Anning	–	Mary	1799	–	1847	–	UK (English)	pt, fossils collector	Elizabeth Philpot	Anning/Philpot connection; C. Murchison
Arner-Boyd	–	Louise	1887	–	1972	–	USA	geogr, scientific explorer	–	–
Atkinson	Calvert	Louisa	1834		1872	–	Australian	ill, fossil collector, b	–	–
Baber	–	Zonia (Mary A.)	1862	–	1956	–	USA	g, geogr	–	–
Bancroft	–	Nellie				–	UK	pb	–	–
Barnard	Greenly	An(nie)	1852	1891	1927	–	UK (English)	g surveying, petrographist	–	–
Bascom	–	Florence	1862	–	1945	1893	USA	g: mineral, petrographist	–	–
Bate	–	Dorothea M. A.	1878	–	1951	–	UK	pt (vertebrate)	–	Dorothy Garrod (n.g.)
Belaeva	–	Elizaveta I.	1894		1983	–	Ru	pt	–	–
Benett	–	Etheldred	1775	–	1845	–	UK	pt, strati, g	–	–
Benson	–	Margaret	1859	–	1936	–	UK	pb	–	Ethel Sargant (n.g.)
Bentivoglio	–	Marie				–	Australian	mineral	–	Frieda Frances Friederich
Berridge	–	Emily M				–	UK	pb, b	–	–
Birley	–	Caroline	1851	–	1907	–	UK (English)	pt, fossils collector	–	L. Copland
Blackburn	–	Kathleen B.	1892	–	1968	1924 (D.)	UK	gl g, mainly b	–	sister Dorothy
Bliss	Knopf	Eleanora	1883	1920	1974	1912	USA	petro (structural)	Florence Bascom	–
Bolton	Helsby	Edith	1893	1930	1974	–	UK	pb	–	M. C. Tuck
Bowdick	Lee	Sarah W.	1791	1812	1856	–	UK	popularizer & « amateur » g	–	–
Brenchley	–	Winifred E.	1883		1953	–	UK	pb, b	–	–
Brezina	–	Maria A.	1848		1909	–	Austrian	mineral & crystallo	–	–
Brown	Browne	Ida	1900	1950	1976	1932 (D.)	Australian	petro-mineral, pt, strati	–	Dorothy Hill (t.y.)
Buckley	Fisher	Arabella	1840	1884	1929	–	UK (English)	teacher, ill	–	M. Somerville
Bullock	Workman	Fanny	1859	1881	1925	–	USA	alpine explorer, gl g, glaciologist	–	daughter R. Workman McRobert
Butler	–	Elenor				–	Irish	teacher	–	–

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last name	last name (married)	first name	birth	marr.	death	PhD/Dsc	nationality	discipline- subject	mentored by a woman	pair sorority ?
Carter	Edson	Fanny	1887	<1924	1952	–	USA	petrol g		
Cary	Agassiz	Elizabeth C.	1822	1850	1907	–	USA	natural his		M. Horner Lyell
Céline	Leclercq	Suzanne	1901				Belgian	pb, pt		
Chaudet		Maria C.	??		1947		Argentinian	g		
Chorley	Crosfield	Margaret	1859		1952	–	UK	pt, strati		Newnham quartet
Cohen		Fanny	1887		1975	–	Australian	mineral	–	
Congreve	–	Sarah	1737	–	1836	–	UK (English)	fossils collector		Anning/Philpot connection
Congreve	–	Mary	1745	–	1823	–	UK (English)	fossils collector		Anning/Philpot connection
Cookson		Isabel C.	1893		1973	1932 (D.)	Australian	pb, palynologist	–	G. Elles
Copland	–	Louisa		–		–	UK	fossils collector		C. Birley
Cotter	–	E.		–		–	Irish	mineral		
Crane		Agnes	1852			–	UK	pt	–	–
Crawford-MacDowall	Wright	Mabel		1914		–	UK	pt		
Crespin		Irene	1896		1980	1960 (D. h.)	Australian	pt (μ), petrol g	–	I. Cookson; J. Gilbert-Tomlinson (t.y.)
Crié	Oehlert	Pauline E.	1854	1874	1911	–	French	pt		
De Fraine		Ethel				–	UK	pb, b	–	
Delvalle	Lowry	Rebekah	1761		1848	–	UK (English)	mineral		M. Somerville
Dingwall	Harrison	Janet M. M.	1893	1939	1971	–	UK	pt		
Dix	–	Emily	1904	–	1972	1933	UK (Welsh)	pb		
Dobbie	Curie	Ethel	1899		1963		UK (Scottish)	g		H. Muir-Wood; C. Duncan McCallien
Dobrolubova	–	Tatiana	1891	–	1972	–	Ru	g, pt	–	–
Donald	Longstaff	Jane	1855	1906	1935	–	UK (English)	pt	–	E. Anderson Grey
Dowell	Stearns	Norah	1890	~1925		1916	USA	hydrog		M. Foster
Drew		Helen	1881		1927	–	UK (English)	pt, g		I. Slater Lees; Newnham Quartet extended
Drummond-Smith	Cotton	Catherine	~1890	~1919	~1950	–	Australian	pt		
Edinger	–	Tilly	1897	–	1967	1921	German-USA	pt		
Elles	–	Gertrude L.	1872	–	1960	1907 (D.)	UK (English-Sc.)	pt, strati, field g		Newnham quartet; K. McNerny Sherrard
Ellisor	–	Alva C.	1892	–	1964	–	USA	petrol g, μ-pt, strati	Julia Gardner	E. Richards Applin; H. Kniker
Eyton	–	Charlotte	1839	–	1917	–	UK	gl g		
Fairfax	Somerville	Mary	1780		1872	–	UK (Scottish)	physical geogr, maths, astron	Rebekah Delvalle Lowry	M. Graham, Ada Lovelace (n.g.)
Fisher	–	Elizabeth F.	1873	–	1941	–	USA	g, geogr		–
Foley		Cecilia M.			1925	–	UK	g		
Folmer	–	Hermine J.	1882	–		–	Dutch	geophysicist		
Forster	–	Mary		–		–	UK	g		
Foster		Margaret				–	USA	chemist		N. Dowell Stearns

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Fowler-	Billings	Katherine (Kay) S.	1902	1929	1997	1930	USA	g	Florence Bascom	
Francis	Child	Lydia M.	1802		1880	–	USA	g		
Fritz	–	Madeleine A.	1896	–	1990	1926	Canadian	pt, field work	Alice Wilson	A. Wilson
Fuller	Boos	Margaret B.	1892	1927	1978	1924	USA	petrol g, strati, structural g	–	–
Furlani	Cornelius	Marta	1886	1921	1974		Austrian	structural g & strati		
Gardiner	–	Margaret I.	1860	–	1944	–	UK	g		
Gardner	–	Julia A.	1882	–	1960	1911	USA	pt, petrol biostrati	Florence Bascom	A. Jonas Stose; E. Bliss Knopf
Gardner	–	Elinor W.	1892		1981	–	UK	g, anthropologist, b		
Goldring	–	Winifred	1888	–	1971	1957 (h.)	USA	pb	Elizabeth F. Fisher	
Goodyear	–	Edith	1879		1959	–	UK	strati	–	
Gordon-	Cumming	Eliza M.	1795		1842	–	UK (Scottish)	pt, ill		daughter Anne Seymour
Gortynskaia	Pavlova	Maria V.	1854	1886	1938	1916 (h.)	Ru (Ukrainian or.)	pt	–	mentor to many
Graham	Callcott	Maria	1785		1842	–	UK	g, b		M. Somerville, J. Marcet
Gray	–	Edith				–	UK (Scottish)	fossils collector	mother E. Anderson	sister Alice
Gray	–	Alice				–	UK (Scottish)	fossils collector	mother E. Anderson	sister Edith
Guppy	–	Eileen	1903	–	1980	–	UK	petro, analytical chemist	–	–
Heermann	–	Margareta	1898	–	1957		Hungarian	g, mineral		
Hendricks	–	Eileen M. L.	1888	–	1978	1932	UK	strati		
Hodgson	–	Elizabeth	1814		1877	–	UK	g		
Hofmann	–	Elise	1889		1955	1924	Austrian	pt & palynologist		
Holmes	–	Mary Emily	1850	–	1906	1888	USA	g, pt, educator, b	–	–
Hone	Smith	Mary	1784		1866	–	UK	fossils collector		
Horner	Lyell	Mary	1808	1832	1873	–	UK	g		E. Cary Agassiz
Howard	Wyldi	Hildegarde	1901	1930	1997	1926	USA	pt		
Hoyermann	–	Tekla				–	German	g		
Hugonin	Murchison	Charlotte	1788	1815	1869	–	UK (Scottish)	g, pt	–	M. Somerville, M. Anning
Hult	de Geer	Ebba	1882	1908	1969	–	Swedish	palæoclimatologist		
Hüther	Richter	Emma	1888		1956	1949 (h.)	German	pt		
Jewell-Glass	–	Jeannette	1888	–	1966	–	USA	mineral		
Johnston	–	Mary S.	1875		1955		UK (English)	pt, g	–	Newnham Quartet extended
Jonas	Stose	Anna	1881	1938	1974	1912	USA	petro	Florence Bascom	E. Bliss Knopf, J. Gardner
Kaplanova	Slavikova	Ludmila	1890	1917	1943	1914	Czechoslovakian	mineral, crystallo, economic g		–
Kelly	–	Agnes	~1875			1900	UK (Australian or.)	g		
Kemper	Palmer	Dorothy B.	1897	1923	1947	–	USA	petrol g		
King	–	Georgina	1845	–	1932	–	Australian	anthropo, strati, economic g	–	–

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Kingdon	Heslop	Mary	1884		1954	–	UK (Egyptian or.)	mineral, igneous petro, geogr	Catherine Raisin	
Kingsley		Louise	1899		1968	1931	USA	g	Florence Bascom	K. Fowler-Billings
Klaassen	Scott	Henderina V.	??	1887	1929	–	UK	pb, b	–	
Klenova		Maria K	1898		1976	?	Ru	marine g		
Knaggs		Isobel				–	South African	crystallo		
Kniker	–	Hedwig T.	1891	–	1985	–	USA	petrol g, pt	–	E. Richards Applin; A. Ellisor
Knote	Ebers	Edith	1894		1974	–	German	gl g, geomorphologist		
Lane	Weinzierl	Laura L.	1900	1923	1928	–	USA	petrol g, pt	–	E. Richards Applin
Le Maître	–	Dorothee	1896	–	1990	–	French	pt & g		
Lehmann	–	Inge	1888	–	1993	1964 (h.)	Danish	seismologist		
Lindsey		Marjorie				–	UK	pb	–	
Livesey	Reynolds Holmes	Doris	1899	1939	1985	–	UK	petro	Catherine Raisin	
Lowry	Varley	Delvalle E.	1800	1825	1859	–	UK (English)	mineral		
Mason	–	Carol Y.	1902	–	1956	1936	USA	g, geogr		
Maury	–	Carlotta J.	1874	–	1938	1902	USA (Brazil or.)	pt		
Maximilianovna	Rauzer-Chernousova	Dagmara	1895		1996	1945	Ru	g, pt		
McGlamery		Josie W.	1887		1977	–	USA	g, pt	–	–
McInerney	Sherrard	Kathleen	1898	1928	1975	–	Australian	pt, strati	–	G. Elles; Joan Crockford Beattie (t.y.)
Mertz		Ellen L.	1896		1987	–	Danish	engineering geology pioneer	–	
Mikhailovna	Shubnikova	Olga	1884	<1920	1955	1936	Ru	mineral		
Milne	Prestwich (McCall)	Grace	1832	1854	1899	–	UK (Scottish)	g		M. Somerville
Missuna		Anna B.	~1868		1922	–	Polish-Ru	g (gl), pt, mineral	–	
Morland	Buckland	Mary	1797	1825	1857	–	UK (English)	pt, ill	–	M. Anning ?
Muir-Wood	–	Helen M.	1896	–	1968	–	UK	pt, hist of palæontology	–	E. Dobbie Curie
Munro		Madeline				–	UK	pt		
Neuburg		Maria F.	1894		1962	1948	Ru	pb, strati		
Newton	Foote	Eunice	1819	1841	1888	–	USA	atmospheric chemist		
Nikolayevna	Sokolskaya	Anna	1901		1971	–	Ru	g, pt, hydrog		
O'Connell		Marjorie	~1900	~1928		1916	USA	pt		
Ogilvie	Gordon	Maria M. (May)	1864	1895	1939	D:1893/1900	UK (Scottish)	pt, structural g, alpine g	–	–
Ogilvie	–	Ida Helen	1874	–	1963	1903	USA	gl geomorphologist	Florence Bascom	
Owen		Luella A.	1852		1932	–	USA	speleologist, g	–	sisters Mary (n.g.), Julietta (n.g.)
Pengelly	Julian	Hester F.	1865	1902		–	UK	g		
Peyronnet-Browne	–	Isabel	1881	–	1947	–	UK (English)	pb, b	Agnes Robertson Arber	
Phillips	–	Anne	1803	–	1862	–	UK (English)	g	–	–

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Philpot	–	Mary /Louise	1777	–	1838	–	UK (English)	pt, fossils collector		M. Anning
Philpot	–	Elizabeth	1780	–	1857	–	UK (English)	pt, fossils collector		M. Anning
Philpot	–	Margaret	1786	–	1845	–	UK (English)	pt, fossils collector		M. Anning
Powell		Dorothy K. 'Dip'	1898			–	Australian	pt		
Prankerd		Theodora L.	1878		1939	–	UK	pb, b	–	
Quodling		Florence M.	1901		1985	–	Australian	mineral		
Radler	Hall	Dollie	1897		1955	–	USA	petrol g		–
Raisin	–	Catherine	1855	–	1945	1898 (D.)	UK (English)	mineral, metamorphic petro		Newnham Quartet extended
Richards	Applin	Esther	1895		1972	–	USA	petrol g	Julia Gardner	A. Ellisor; H. Kniker; L. Lane Weinzierl
Robertson	Arber	Agnes	1879	1909	1960	1905 (D.)	UK	pb, b	–	Ethel Sargant (n.g.); M. Benson
Rudbeck	Arrhenius	Sofia	1866	1894	1937	–	Swedish	g		
Sahlbom	–	Naima	1871	–	1957	1910	Swedish	mineral, geochemist		
Sanborn	–	Ethel	??	–	1952	1927	USA	pb, b		
Scarpollini		Caterina	1808		1872	–	Italian	meteorologist, astronomer		
Shirokobrumov	Tumanskaya	Olga	1888		1970	1923	Ru	g, pt	–	–
Shulga	Nesterenko	Maria I.	1891		1964	–	Ukrainian	g, pt		
Sieverts	Doreck	Hertha	1899	1936	1991	1927	German	pt	–	–
Skeat	Woods	Ethel	1865	1910	1939	1905 (h.)	UK	pt, strati		Newnham quartet
Skewes	Plummer	Helen J.	1891		1951	–	USA	petrol g, μ -pt	–	–
Slater	Lees	Ida L.	1881	1912	1969	–	UK	g, pt	Catherine Raisin	H. Drew; G. Elles; C. Raisin
Smith	–	Isabel F.	1890	–	1990	1923	USA	g, historian of geology	Florence Bascom	
Sollas	–	Igerna B. J.	1877	–	1965	–	UK	natural scientist & g		
Solomko	Viktorovna	Evgenia	1862		1898	1887	Ru	pt, petrographist	–	–
Soshkina		Elizabeth D.	1889		1963	1946 (h.)	Ru	g, pt, biologist		
Stadnichenko	–	Taisia (Maria) M.	1894	–	1958	–	Ru-USA	petrol g, μ -pt, geochemist	Florence Bascom	
Stefanescu		Sabba	1857		1931	–	Rumanian	pt, strati		
Stevens	Walcott	Helene B.	1868	1888	1911	–	USA	g, pt	–	–
Stewart	–	Grace Anne	1893	–	1970	1922	Canadian	pt, strati		
Stopes	Roe	Marie C. C.	1880		1958	1904	UK (Scottish)	pb, coal g	–	
Swallow	Richards	Ellen	1842		1911	–	USA	mineral, water chemist	–	Maria Mitchell (n.g.)
Syniewska		Janina	1893		1951	–	Polish	g, μ pt		
Talbot		Mignon	~1869		1950	1904	USA	g, pt		
Thomas	Williams	Marguerite	1895	1931	1991	1942	USA	g, geogr, social sciences	–	–
Thomas Carne	–	Elizabeth C.	1817		1873	–	UK (Cornwall)	g	–	–
Thompson	Christen	Sydney M.	1847	1900	1923	–	Irish	gl g	–	M. Andrews

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Todtmann		Emmy M.	1888		1973	–	German	gl g		
Tomlinson	–	Mabel E.		–		1929	UK (English)	strati, IV sedimentologist		
Trizna	–	Valentina B.	1892	–		–	Ru	g, pt, hydrog	–	–
Tschernaieff	Jérémine	Elisabeth	1879		1964	1911	French-Ru	g, petro	–	J. Pfeder
Tsvetaeva		Maria	1854			–	Ru	pt		–
Tuck		Margaret C				–	UK	pb		E. Bolton
Turutanova-Ketova		Antonina I.	1896		1973	–	Ru	pb		
Van Winckle	Palmer	Katherine E. H.	1895	1921	1982	–	USA	g	–	
Varsanofeva		Vera A.	1890	–	1976	1935	Ru (French or.)	g	–	–
Vaux	Walcott	Mary M.	1860	1914	1940	–	USA	gl g, b	–	Mary Schäffer (n.g.); Lou Henry Hoover
Vernon	Cole	Blanche	1862	1896	1927	–	Irish	drawings (petrography)	–	–
Viktorovna Karpova	Semikhatova	Sofia	1889	1913	1973	–	Ru	g, pt		
Vincent		Adele V.	1896			–	Australian	pb		
Vladimirovna	Lermontova	Ekaterina	1899		1942	–	Ru	pt		
Welleck	Garretson	Mary	1896	1922	1971	–	USA	pt, journalist		
Weston	McKenny Hugues	Mary C.	1860	1882	1916	–	UK	g		
Whedon		Frances L.	1902			–	USA	meteorologist		
White	Hitchcock	Orra	1796	1821	1863	–	USA	ill g & b		
Wigglesworth	–	Grace		–		–	UK	pb, b	–	
Wills	–	Lucy	1888	–	1964	–	UK (English)	pb, then physician	–	Margaret Hume (n.g.)
Wilson	–	Alice E.	1881	–	1964	1929	Canadian	g	–	Canadian Fed. of Uni. Women
Winearls Porter	–	Mary	1886	–	1980	1932 (D.)	UK (English)	crystallo	Florence Bascom	Dorothy Hodgkin (chemist)
Wood	Shakespeare	Ethel	1871	1906	1946	–	UK	pt, strati		Newnham quartet
Woodhouse	Mantell	Mary Ann	1795	1816	1869	–	UK	pt, ill, fossils collector		
Woodward	–	Gertrude M.	1854	–	1939	–	UK	ill (professional)		
Woodward	–	Alice B.	1862	–	1951	–	UK	ill (professional)		
Workman	MacRobert	Rachel	1884		1954	–	USA	mineral, igneous petro	mother F. Bullock	C. Raisin; M. Ogilvie Gordon
Wyckoff		Dorothy	1900		1982	1932	USA	mineral	Florence Bascom	n.g.: Jane Oppenheimer, Dorothy Burr Thompson
Wynne Edwards	Reid	Eleanor M.	1860	1897	1953	–	UK	pb		Marjorie Chandler (t.y.)
Yakobevna	Polubarinova-Kochina	Pelageya	1899	1925	1999	1940	Ru	hydrologist, mathematician		
Yelverton	Hastings	Barbara	1810	1831	1858	–	UK	strati, pt, fossils collector		
Zaniewska	Chlipalska	Eugenia	1889	~1928	1980	–	Polish	mineral, igneous petro, pedo.	–	
Zenaki		Silvia	1895		1956	–	Italian	biologist & g		
Zlatarovic		Rely				–	Austrian	meteorologist, chemist		

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Amalitskiya		Anna P.	1861		1939	—	Ru	g		
Cole		Mary L.	1775		1855	—	UK	g		
Kablik		Josephine E.	1787	1806	1863	—	Czech	pt & b		
Mirchink		Maria E.	1887		1978	—	Ru	g	Maria Pavlova	A. Missuna
Selenka -Heinemann		Margarethe L.	1860	1893			German	pt		
Talbot		Jane				—	UK (Welsh)	g		